

EDUCATION AND CULTURE

THE CULTURAL DIVERSITY OF YUAN DYNASTY MONGOLIAN TRADITIONAL COSTUME COLORS: THE CASE OF JISUM ROBES

La diversidad cultural de los colores de los trajes tradicionales mongoles de la dinastía Yuan: el caso de las túnicas Jisum

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ABSTRACT

Background: Jisum robes, as a model of Yuan dynasty Mongolian aristocrat ceremonial costume, focuses on the diversity of colors and cultural symbolism of Yuan dynasty costumes. Based on the combing of historical documents, this study systematically analyzes the color composition of Jisum robes, cultural origin, and its cultural tourism potential. **Methods:** This study adopts a systematic historical document analysis to explore the hierarchical symbolism, ceremonial functions, and cultural diversity of the Jisum robes' color system during the Yuan Dynasty. **Results:** It is found that the color system of Jisum robes integrates the elements of traditional Mongolian, Central Asian and Han cultures, which not only shows the multi-ethnic cultural fusion of the Yuan Dynasty but also forms a unique ceremonial dress system and becomes a symbol of multi-cultural exchange. **Conclusion:** This knowledge can be a potential for tourism that implements interactive experiences based on interactive story telling. Cultural diversity, jisum colour system, which integrates traditional Mongolian, Han Chinese, and Central Asian influences. These robes symbolize a unique cultural fusion, with colours representing power, purity, and social hierarchy, thereby underscoring their ceremonial significance gives the potential of Jisum robes to serve as a medium for cultural tourism and education through storytelling-based tourism.

KEY WORDS

Yuan Dynasty, Mongolian Traditional Costumes, Jisum Robes, Color, Culture Diversity.

RESUMEN

Antecedentes: Las túnicas Jisum, como modelo del traje ceremonial de la aristocracia mongola de la dinastía Yuan, se centran en la diversidad de colores y el simbolismo cultural de los trajes de la dinastía Yuan. A partir de la revisión de documentos históricos, este estudio analiza sistemáticamente la composición cromática de las túnicas Jisum, su origen cultural y su potencial para el turismo cultural. **Métodos:** Este estudio adopta un análisis sistemático de documentos históricos para explorar el simbolismo jerárquico, las funciones ceremoniales y la diversidad cultural del sistema de colores de las túnicas Jisum durante la dinastía Yuan. **Resultados:** Se ha descubierto que el sistema de colores de las túnicas Jisum integra elementos de las culturas tradicionales mongola, centroasiática y han, lo que no solo muestra la fusión cultural multiétnica de la dinastía Yuan, sino que también conforma un sistema de vestimenta ceremonial único y se convierte en un símbolo del intercambio multicultural. **Conclusión:** Este conocimiento puede ser un potencial para el turismo que implementa experiencias interactivas basadas en la narración interactiva. Diversidad cultural, sistema de colores Jisum, que integra influencias tradicionales mongolas, chinas han y centroasiáticas. Estas túnicas simbolizan una fusión cultural única, con colores que representan poder, pureza y jerarquía social, lo que subraya su importancia ceremonial y da el potencial de las túnicas Jisum para servir como medio para el turismo cultural y la educación a través del turismo basado en la narración de historias.

PALABRAS CLAVE

Dinastía Yuan, Trajes tradicionales mongoles, Túnicas Jisum, Color, Diversidad cultural.

INTRODUCTION

The Yuan Dynasty was the first unified dynasty in Chinese history established by ethnic minorities, with its territory spanning the Eurasian continent, and the multi-ethnic cultural intermingling under the regime was extremely significant. In this context, costume, as an important symbol of social identity, political power, and cultural exchange, became an important entry point for understanding the cultural system of the Yuan Dynasty. As the ruling ethnic group of the Yuan Dynasty, the traditional costumes of the Mongols, while maintaining their own cultural characteristics, absorbed a variety of cultural elements from the Han culture of the Central Plains and Central Asia, forming a unique costume system.

Color is the most expressive part of the Yuan Dynasty costume culture, which not only reflects the traditional aesthetic concepts of the Mongols, but also plays an important role in social hierarchies, religious ceremonies, and cross-cultural exchanges. In the analysis of the cultural diversity of the color of Mongolian traditional costumes in the Yuan Dynasty, Jisum robes is undoubtedly one of the most representative examples, which concentrates on the use of color and cultural symbols of the Mongolian nobility in ceremonial costumes, and becomes an important entry point to understand the costume system and aesthetic concepts in this period (As shown in Figure 1).

Figure 1: Ceremonial Scene of the Hundred Officials Wearing Jisum Robes (Mongol costume).

In recent years, scholars' research on Jisum robes mainly focuses on its ceremonial function, color system and cultural symbols. Studies have shown that the Jisum robes embodied the hierarchical order with the system of "one color per day", and its color system integrated the Mongolian tradition, the concept of "five colors" of Chinese culture and the luxury style of Central Asian culture, which became the symbol of multiculturalism in the Yuan Dynasty. However, these studies are more limited to static descriptions and lack analysis of the dynamic use of

color in different ceremonial occasions. In addition, the specific embodiment of Jisum robes color system in the process of cross-cultural dissemination and integration has not been thoroughly studied.

The potential of this colour's cultural uniqueness, aesthetics and rich meaning to attract interest is worthy of consideration. The reinstatement of the joy of Jisum's ceremonial function in today's context, as a means of introducing culture through tourism, is a promising avenue for further research. The integration of storytelling in educational tourism, which is characterised by its significance, has the capacity to facilitate the transmission of cultural narratives through this medium. However, it is essential to ensure that storytelling is presented in the correct form to ensure the effective conveyance of the rich culture embedded in this clothing. Based on this, this paper takes Jisum robes as an example to explore the cultural diversity embodied in its color system in Mongolian costumes of the Yuan Dynasty and how it's can be a potential story based tourism. This study will be centered on the following two research questions:

- What are the characteristics of the color system of Jisum robes?
- How do these colors reflect cultural diversity?
- How is the story-based tourism can be applied

The objectives of this study are to reveal the symbolic meaning and dynamic use of the colors of Jisum robes through the analysis of literature and reconstruction of historical situations, and to explore the static characteristics and dynamic laws of the color system in the Yuan Dynasty ceremonial dress Jisum robes from the perspective of cultural diversity.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Yuan Dynasty was a pivotal period of multi-ethnic cultural fusion, where costume culture showcased the interaction of Mongolian traditions, Chinese Central Plains culture, and Central Asian influences. Jisum robes, as the ceremonial attire of Mongolian aristocracy, reflected both hierarchical order and cultural symbolism through their structured color system, exemplifying the integration of diverse cultural elements.

While previous research has explored the ceremonial role, symbolic hierarchy, and color diversity of Jisum robes, limitations remain in understanding their dynamic color usage, symbolism, and broader cultural connotations. This study addresses these gaps by reviewing existing literature across four themes: ceremonial functions, hierarchical symbols, color diversity, and multicultural influences.

Ceremonial Function and Hierarchical Symbols

It is widely believed that the Jisum robes reinforced the hierarchical order of the Yuan ceremonial scene through the system of “one color for one day”. Li points out that the color distribution of Jisum robes strictly follows the status of the wearer, for example, red and yellow symbolize imperial power and authority, while green and white are used for attendants and guards (Li, 2008). Fan further points out that the dynamic color rules of Jisum robes not only reflect the need to visualize hierarchical differentiation, but also enhance the sense of order in the ceremonial scene. However, most of these studies remain in the superficial analysis of hierarchical symbols, and lack the details of the actual implementation of the “one color per day” system, such as the specific time of implementation, how to choose the colors, and their adaptability to different scenes (Fan, 2022). Liang reveals the high frequency of the use of red and blue by counting the frequency of color words in the History of the Yuan Dynasty and the Records of Public Apparel, but there is a lack of further explanation as to how these colors served the ceremonial function in terms of visual effects (Liang, 2020).

Color System and Cultural Diversity

The multicultural context of Jisum robes colors has been widely recognized, but existing research still has some shortcomings. The Mongolian concept of nature worship gives blue and white an important place, which is emphasized in the study of Su and Yao, who explores the cultural symbols of the Jisum robes through Yuan dynasty poetry, describing color symbolism and multicultural integration (Su & Yao, 2023). This study is mainly based on Mongolian cultural traditions, and the exploration of how blue and white are represented in the ceremonial design of the Jisum robes and how they are intermingled with other cultural elements is still insufficient.

In addition, the influence of Han culture’s “five positive colors” concept on Jisum robes has been confirmed by several studies (Chen, 2017; Liang, 2020), but further empirical evidence is still lacking as to whether this influence stems from direct cultural inheritance or indirect adaptive adjustments. While the influence of Central Asian and Persian cultures on Jisum robes has been mentioned several times, such as the use of green and gold colors, specific transmission paths and technical details remain blank in the existing literature (Dong, 2016). Lin’s study also explores the process of the formation and spread of the color system of Jisum robes, suggesting that the dyeing and weaving techniques and decorative arts of Central Asia and Persia were introduced to the Yuan Dynasty via the

Silk Road, which had a profound impact on the production of Jisum robes (Lin et al., 2018). This view reveals the important role of Central Asian culture in the Yuan Dynasty dress craft, especially its outstanding contribution in color expression and decorative techniques. However, the study is still insufficient in discussing the details of specific transmission paths and technological integration, such as the interaction process between Central Asian and Mongolian dress traditions in technological transformation has not yet been clarified.

Multiculturalism and Technology Integration

The characteristic cultural cross-fertilization in the design concept and production process of the Jisum robes has been recognized in a large body of literature. Chen (2017) points out that the use of Nasich brocade reflects the combination of Central Asian craftsmanship with Mongolian traditions, but how this craft is localized among Mongolian artisans and the Mongolian initiative in adapting the technology still needs to be further discussed (Chen, 2017). Li (2011) analysis of Jisum robes fabrics reveals their material diversity (Li, 2011), but there is a lack of more in-depth exploration of how these materials can be optimized for use in ceremonial scenarios, and in particular, it is not yet clear whether the combination of silk and fur products is related to seasonal or situational demands.

Fan suggests from an artistic point of view that the integration of color and craftsmanship in Jisum robes focuses on the fruits of multi-ethnic cultural exchange and highlights the importance of color and decoration in ritual expression (Fan, 2022). This study does not go far enough in explaining the dynamic relationship between craftsmanship and color symbolism. Specifically, it focuses on the surface presentation of the artistic beauty of Jisum robes, but fails to further explore the interplay between craftsmanship and cultural symbolism, as well as the practical application and significance of this relationship in social contexts. Lin points out that the aesthetic tendencies of Central Asian and Persian cultures brought significant decorative changes to the Jisum robes, an influence that not only enhanced their visual expression, but also endowed them with richer cultural symbols (Lin et al., 2018). However, the text does not analyze in detail how the color system was integrated into the Mongolian ceremonial culture from a foreign technology. In addition, the appropriateness of these decorative hues in Yuan society and culture and their functional transformation process have not been fully explained.

CASE AND METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a systematic historical document

analysis to explore the hierarchical symbolism, ceremonial functions, and cultural diversity of the Jisum robes' color system during the Yuan Dynasty. Given the absence of physical remains of Jisum robes, historical texts serve as the primary source of data, supplemented by relevant image materials to provide a more comprehensive perspective. The research combines an interpretation of official historical records, regional literature, poetry, and travelogues, reconstructing the historical background and socio-cultural context to analyze the composition, evolution, and significance of the color system.

The primary textual sources include Yuan Shi, Liao, Jin, and Yuan Poems, and various travel accounts. These documents are systematically examined to identify references to the Jisum robes' color system, focusing on its role in ceremonial practices, hierarchical symbolism, and cultural integration. Through comparative analysis, discrepancies and consistencies between various historical accounts are addressed, revealing the practical application and dynamic use of color in Yuan court rituals.

The study also investigates the multicultural symbolism embedded within the Jisum robes' color system. By tracing influences from Mongolian traditional color concepts, the Han Chinese "Five Standard Colors," and Central Asian decorative techniques, it reveals how color distribution and dynamic variation served to reinforce ritual order and cultural diversity within the Yuan Mongol court. Special attention is given to the "one color per day" system described in historical texts, uncovering its underlying cultural connotations and dynamic usage patterns

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of the Color System of Jisum Robes

Jisum robes originated from the Jisum banquet, also known as the Zhama Banquet, which was a unique court feast in the Mongol Yuan period. In the Jisum robes, all participants must wear Jisum robes to participate in the feast. This tradition originally originated from the Mongolian steppe tribal gathering culture, early gatherings for marriage, rituals, military discussions and other important matters and convene. With the establishment and expansion of the Mongol empire, such tribal gatherings gradually evolved into institutionalized national ceremonial activities, which not only assumed the function of political consultation, but also became an important occasion for the Mongolian nobility to demonstrate their status and authority (Li, 2022).

Jisum robes, also known as "Jisum" (Mongolian Jisum), according to *Yuan history of Treatise on Carriages and Attire* records: "Jisum, the Han

language, one-color clothes." (Song, 1976a), *Yuan History of Treatise on Rituals and Music* also said, "The clothes of the pre-feast, clothes with the same system, called the Jisum." (Song, 1976b), "clothes with the system" refers to the Jisum robes worn at the feast of Jisum robes with the same color, style fabrics can be different. Jisum banquet with Jisum robes of this dress regulation began in 1229 during the reign of Wukodai, to the Kublai period Jisum robes become important ceremonial occasions of the royal family and the nobility of the costume norms, and further luxury.

The records of Jisum robes in historical documents are primarily found in Yuan Dynasty poetry, travelers' travelogues, and the official History of the Yuan Dynasty. This study systematically analyzes the color system's characteristics and cultural diversity based on these sources.

Static Characteristics of the Color System of Jisum Robes

The color system of Jisum robes demonstrates the distinctive features of Mongolian ceremonial costumes in the Yuan Dynasty, and its static features are mainly reflected in the types of colors, distribution patterns and their symbolic meanings. As the necessary ceremonial dress in the Jisum robes, the color choice of the Jisum robes not only reflects the solemnity and beauty of the ceremonial occasion, but also deeply reflects the unique understanding of the Mongolian people on nature and culture.

Yuan history of *Treatise on Carriages and Attire* highlights that : "Hundred officials of the quality of Sun, the winter clothing where nine equal, big red Nasij one, big red Qiemianli one, big red crown one, peach red, blue-green official one, purple, yellow, raven green one jujube brown pistachio gold between silk clams pearl one" (Song, 1976b, p. 198). As we can see, red is the most commonly used color for Jisum robes because of its bright visual effect and auspicious symbolism, and is considered to be the most representative of the Mongolian color concept, As illustrated in the Figure 2, the majority of emperors are depicted wearing red Jisum robes. Brown was also used in Jisum robes for its natural origin and richness, symbolizing the simplicity of grassland life. Blue and green held important roles, while rarer colors like raven green and purple were reserved for specific occasions or classes.

Although *the History of Yuan Dynasty-Yufuzhi* does not explicitly list white among the colors for Jisum robes of the hundred officials, this omission may result from incomplete documentation, given the Mongols' traditional reverence for white.

The incomplete list of fabrics in the Treatise suggests the color system of Jisum robes likely included unrecorded colors. Other records, such as *Supplementary Notes to the Wutai Records*, highlight the significance of white in Yuan clothing, noting its role in ceremonial attire and its association with Mongol cultural traditions, symbolizing purity, fortune, and sanctity (Wang, 1957). Based on visual evidence, the depiction of Yuan Taizu wearing a white Jisum robe further substantiates this argument, as shown in Figure 3.

the ceremonial and cultural significance of white as a traditional Jisum robe color.

Figure 2: Portraits of Yuan Dynasty Emperors (Illustrated Treatise on Carriages and Attire: Yuan History).

Figure 3: The Portrait of Genghis Khan (Illustrated Treatise on Carriages and Attire: Yuan History).

Further evidence comes from the account of the Italian missionary John Plano Garbini. During his mission to the Great Mongol Empire in 1246, he witnessed the great feast of the prime grandson at the ceremony of Guiyu Khan's accession and recorded in his travelogue, "On the first day, they all wore white velvet" (Dawson, 1983, p. 60). This record highlights the Mongols' preference for white and complements the limited color details of Jisum robes in *Yuan History Treatise on Carriages and Attire*. Together, these materials underscore

Ke Jiushi mentioned in *Palace Poems of the Liao, Jin, and Yuan Dynasties*, "thousands of officials a color of the real pearl jacket, the treasure belt to save the clothes stable waist" (Ke, 1988), "Thousands of officials a color" is a record from Zhama banquet, highlighting the uniformity of Jisum robes' color. *Yuan History* specifies that during the Jisum banquet, robes must be of the same color. This rule reflects the solemnity of Mongolian ceremonial concepts and enhances the symbolic significance of the Qisun Banquet through a unified visual effect. Based on the *History of Yuan Dynasty·Yufuzhi* and related documents, Table 1 summarizes the main color features of Jisum robes and their static-level characteristics.

Table 1: Static Characteristics of Jisum Robes Color.

Color	Color Subcategories	Symbolism	Classes	Historical Sources
Red	Crimson Peach Red Bright Red	Passion Power Celebration	Emperor	<i>History of Yuan Dynasty·Yufuzhi</i> ; <i>Nancun Records of Leisure from Farming</i>
Brown	Pearl Brown Silvery Brown	Steady High-Class	Officials Commoners	<i>History of Yuan Dynasty·Yufuzhi</i> ; <i>Nancun Records of Leisure from Farming</i>
White	Silvery White Pure White	Auspiciousness Purity Sacred	Emperor Royal Nobility	<i>History of Yuan Dynasty·Yufuzhi</i> ; <i>Supplementary Notes to the Wutai Records</i>
Blue	Deep Blue Sky Blue	Heaven Eternity Solemnity	Emperor Officials	<i>History of Yuan Dynasty·Yufuzhi</i> ; <i>Report of a mission to Mongolia</i>
Green	Light Green Deep Green	Vitality Nature	Guards Attendants	<i>History of Yuan Dynasty·Yufuzhi</i> ; <i>Records of Eastern Travels</i>
Crow Blue	-	Rare Unique	Emperor	<i>History of Yuan Dynasty·Yufuzhi</i>
Purple	-	Nobility Luxury	Emperor Nobility	<i>History of Yuan Dynasty·Yufuzhi</i>
Yellow	-	Imperial Power Nobility	Emperor	<i>History of Yuan Dynasty·Yufuzhi</i>
Cyan	Light Cyan Deep Cyan	Freshness Calmness	Emperor Officials	<i>History of Yuan Dynasty·Yufuzhi</i>

Dynamic Law of the Color System of Jisum Robes

The dynamics of the Jisum robes color system is

reflected in the historical documents of the Yuan Dynasty at many levels, especially the unique ceremonial system of "one color for one day".

According to *The History of the World Conqueror*, Ogedai held a grand Jisum banquet in 1229 when he assumed the throne of the Khan, and it is written in the text: "For forty days in a row, they changed into new clothes of different colors every day, and drank bitterly while discussing affairs of state." (Joveyni, 1958). This vivid description not only reveals the core color rules in the Jisum Banquet but also reflects the high value the Mongols placed on color in their ceremonial scenes. This is not just a costume change, but a ceremonial practice that highlights order and hierarchy. The dynamic rule of daily color changes underscores the importance that the Mongol empire placed on uniform ritual norms, while at the same time endowing color with strong symbolic meaning. By carefully arranging the colors, this system visually creates a sense of festive splendor and solemnity and invisibly highlights the majesty of imperial power and the solidity of the ruling order.

The practical implementation of this law of color dynamics is further verified by Gabbini's account. The Italian missionary, who was present at the ceremony of Güyük's accession to the throne in 1246, recorded the scene of Jisum banquet: "On the first day they were all dressed in white velvet, on the second day - the day on which Güyük came to the tabernacle - in red velvet dresses, on the third day they all wore blue velvet dresses, and on the fourth day, the best brocade dresses." (Dawson, 1983). From this description, it can be seen that the core of the color system of the Qisun Banquet lies not only in the stark contrast of the colors themselves, but also in the dynamic turnover that highlights the symbolism of the different stages of the ritual.

Compared with the objective records of historical documents, the Yuan Dynasty poems added more emotions and moods to the dynamic changes of Jisum robes colors from the perspective of literature. For example, Zheng Yong wrote in *the Zhama Fu*: "Sometimes blue turns into green, sometimes crimson turns into red, Light pink and deep purple intermingle with varying trims and decorations, Across three dynasties, fashions have changed thrice, and even within a single day, the colors are ever-changing." (Zheng, 1996). The poem not only delicately depicts the layering and richness of the colors of Jisum robes in the Zhama Banquet, but also vividly demonstrates the solemnity and harmony of the "one color a day" system. In addition, *the Palace Poems of the Liao, Jin, and Yuan Dynasties* in the "Amid the sound of festive music at dawn on a spring day, All at the imperial court are dressed in Jisum robes before the emperor" (Ke, 1988) is elegant strokes to depict the quality of the Jisum

Banquet in the group dress in the magnificent scene, showing the ceremonial dress uniform color brought about by the shocking visual effect. The depictions in these poems, through the interweaving of imagery and emotion, push the aesthetic value and cultural significance of the dynamic law of Jisum robes to a higher level.

Through the historical documents and poems of the Yuan Dynasty, it can be seen that the dynamic law of Jisum robes color has the following three major characteristics: First, the combination of daily color change and ritual, not only a means of strengthening the visual impact, but also through the system of "one color one day" to give the color to the double symbol of time and meaning, thus enhancing the ritual and solemnity; Second, the consistency of group dress, especially in large palace banquets or major ceremonies, is strictly enforced, not only highlighting the clear division of the group hierarchy, but also reflecting the Yuan Dynasty rituals. Secondly, the consistency of the group dress code, especially in large court banquets or major ceremonies in the strict implementation, not only highlights the clear division of the group hierarchy, but also reflects the high degree of standardization and unification of the value orientation of the Yuan dynasty liturgical system; Thirdly, the matching of colors and ceremonial occasions, which is manifested in the fact that the selection and change of colors can accurately correspond to the symbolic needs of specific scenes, such as the red color of ceremonial occasions is warm and auspicious, while the white color symbolizes the purity and sanctity, which reflects the deep integration of the color culture and the ceremonial space. These laws profoundly reveal the unique position of Jisum robes as ceremonial clothing in the Yuan Dynasty cultural system and also provide important clues for the study of the hierarchical concept and social symbolism of Mongolian costume culture.

Cultural Diversity of Jisum Robes Colors

Jisum robes, as the representative of Yuan Dynasty ceremonial costumes, its color system not only reflects the inheritance of Mongolian people's nature worship and traditional culture but also absorbs the color concepts of the Han culture in the Central Plains and the decorative art of the Central Asian culture in the Western region, which demonstrates the diversity of the Yuan Dynasty's costume culture. As an era of multi-ethnic and multi-cultural fusion, the Yuan Dynasty's dress color contains rich cultural significance, which not only shows the unique national identity of the Mongols but also becomes the carrier of cross-cultural communication and fusion. The cultural

diversity of Jisum robes color is reflected in multiple dimensions: from the inheritance of Mongolian color concepts to the integration of the five-color system in the Central Plains, to the application of luxurious dyeing and weaving techniques in Central Asia, each dimension reflects the unique pattern of Yuan Dynasty costume culture.

Inheritance of Mongolian Color Concepts

Mongolian people live in the northern steppe, and their vast and diverse natural environment has profoundly shaped their concept of color. The grassland has four distinct seasons, the endless green of spring and summer, the golden yellow of autumn, the white of winter, and the blue sky and flowing white clouds, which together form a highly saturated and pure natural color system. This visual experience not only enriches the color preference of Mongolians but also becomes the basis of their cultural aesthetics. In this natural background, Mongolian people tend to choose colors with high saturation and strong contrast, which not only satisfy the practical function, but also show the passion and exuberance of the national character.

This concept of color is well inherited and reflected in Jisum robes. *The History of Yuan Dynasty-Yufuzhi* clearly records that Jisum robes used a variety of distinctive colors, including red, white, brown, blue, green, purple, yellow, and raven green, etc. The color system was rich and highly saturated, which not only conformed to the Mongolian people's preference for the pure colors in the natural environment but also demonstrated the pursuit of the aesthetics of their ceremonial costumes. Among them, white, as the most symbolic color in Mongolian culture, is endowed with the connotation of purity and sanctity, and occupies an important position in Jisum robes; and red, because of its

warmth and authoritative symbolism, becomes the most frequently used color in the ceremonial costumes of Yuan Dynasty nobles.

In addition, the traditional Mongolian concept of nature worship has also deeply influenced the color design of Jisum robes. The natural elements of the grassland life, such as blue sky, green grass and white clouds, have become an important source of inspiration for the color of clothing. For example, the blue color not only symbolizes the vast sky, but also carries the Mongolian people's reverence and faith in the sky; the green color implies the vitality of the grassland. The unified use of these colors in the Qisun Banquet not only highlights the cultural traditions of the Mongolian people but also gives colors a higher ceremonial and symbolic value through the dynamic rule of "one color per day".

Influence of Han Culture in Central China

The process of cultural acculturation is often supported by geographical influences, with different cultures often exerting an influence on each other in terms of material choices and clothing designs when they come into contact with one another. An examination of the geographical map (Figure 4) of the Yuan dynasty reveals the existence of close relationships that facilitate acculturation (Dardess, 1972). With its deep historical tradition and ritual system, the Han culture of the Central Plains had an important influence on the color system of Jisum robes in the Yuan Dynasty. In the Yuan Dynasty, a regime dominated by the Mongols, the dress system retained the traditional characteristics of the Mongols and incorporated elements of Han culture (Fan, 2018). This cultural interaction shaped the unique pluralistic and fusion characteristics of Jisum robes, providing an important perspective for the study of the cultural symbols of Yuan dynasty costumes.

Figure 4: Map of Mongol Power in the Yuan Dynasty Regime.

The five positive colors (cyan, red, yellow, white, and black), as the traditional color concepts of the

Han people, have been widely used in ceremonial costumes since the Han Dynasty, and their

symbolism is closely related to social hierarchy. According to *The History of Yuan Dynasty:Yufuzhi*, the frequency of red color in Jisum robes is as high as 26.5% (Li, 2022), which highlights the important position of red color in Jisum robes. The red color among the five positive colors is also highly symbolic in Han culture (Liang, 2020), which suggests that the Han culture of the Central Plains influenced the color system of Jisum robes to a certain extent.

Describing the Jisum robes, *the Odoric's Travels to the East* mentions that "the kings wore costumes of different colors; some in the first row wore green silk; the second row wore crimson; and the third row wore yellow. All of these wore crowns on their heads, and each held a white ivory tablet in his hand, and a golden sash half a span wide around his waist." (Gonzaksai, Odoric, & Gayesudin, 1981), this account reflects the clear distinction between color and hierarchy in Jisum robes, which fits with the idea of symbolizing hierarchical status through color in the Central Han culture. In Central Han culture, colors were not only closely related to social hierarchies but were also used in state administration through strict ceremonial norms. For example, the five positive colors (green, red, yellow, white, and black) have been widely used in ceremonial costumes since the Han Dynasty to show order and hierarchy. The "one color per day" system of Jisum robes in the Yuan Dynasty reflected the uniqueness of Mongolian ceremonial practice and the far-reaching influence of the Han culture of "ruling the country by color" through the unification and dynamic alternation of different colors in major occasions such as the Jisum robes banquets. The design of this color system not only gives solemnity to the rituals but also highlights the important role of color in the symbol of hierarchy and national governance.

The Influence of Central Asian Culture

With its exquisite dyeing and weaving techniques and vivid color art, Central Asian culture had an important influence on Yuan Dynasty costume culture through the Silk Road. In the color system of Jisum robes, the influence of Central Asian culture is mainly reflected in the introduction of noble shades such as green and gold.

Green in the Yuan Dynasty was regarded as a noble color, is strictly prohibited for the use of the common people "noble color". The First Year of Yuanzhen promulgated a ban clearly states: "Liu Fang green Six colors are not allowed to use, not allowed to weave.". *The History of Yuan Dynasty:Yufuzhi* clearly records examples of the use of green in the Jisum robes of the Emperor

and the hundred officials, such as "The Jisum robes of the Emperor: the clothes of Crimson, Peach Red, Purple Blue, and Green Bao Li," and "The public uniforms of the hundred officials: the green robes of the eighth and ninth grades, with no text" (Song, 1976b, p. 198), and furthermore. *the Odoric's Travels to the East* mentioned above also details the wearing of green Jisum robes. The Yuan dynasty's emphasis on the color green was in part influenced by Islamic culture. With more than a million Muslim immigrants entering the Yuan dynasty to engage in commercial and production activities, Islamic culture gradually penetrated into all levels of Yuan society, and this cultural exchange directly influenced the concept of the color of Jisum robes in the Yuan dynasty.

The color system of Jisum robes in the Yuan Dynasty was heavily influenced by Central Asian culture, with the extensive use of gold being particularly notable. This influence is mainly reflected in the use of textiles and its technology centered on the imported "Nasij" (meaning gold brocade) from Central Asia (As shown in Figure 5).

Figure 5: Nasij (Gold, Silk, and Blue-and-White Porcelain: The Fashion and Art of the Marco Polo Era).

The History of Yuan Dynasty:Yufuzhi clearly records that among the Jisum robes of the Emperor and the hundred officials, as many as seven types of fabrics were made of nasij. As a kind of luxurious gold silk brocade, Nasij became an important expression of gold color in Jisum robes because of its shining effect and exquisite patterns.

This importance of gold color is closely related to the technology and aesthetics of Central Asian culture imported into the Yuan Dynasty through the Silk Road. Since Genghis Khan's western conquest, a large number of Central Asian artisans were

migrated to the Yuan Dynasty territory to make Nasij in the official weaving bureau, which provided sufficient technical support and material basis for the production of Jisum robes. The use of Nasij also reflects the far-reaching influence of Central Asian culture on the Yuan Dynasty's concept of color. Nasij brought the Islamic culture's reverence for the color gold into the Yuan Dynasty, so that the gold color in Jisum robes not only continued the Mongolian tradition, but also incorporated elements of foreign cultures, and became an important symbol of the Yuan Dynasty costume's rank and status.

Jisum Robes based tourism: Storytelling and Audience Engagement

The storytelling potential of Jisum robes, particularly in the context of cultural festivals, serves as a powerful tool for engaging audiences (Soonsan, Sungthong, & Phakdee-Auksorn, 2025). By weaving narratives around the colors, designs, and historical significance of these traditional garments (Leong et al., 2024), festival organizers can create immersive experiences that resonate with attendees on multiple levels. Here's how storytelling can effectively engage the audience. Connecting the Past to the Present, Storytelling can provide historical context about the Yuan Dynasty and the significance of Jisum robes within Mongolian culture. By sharing tales of the robes' origins, their use in ceremonies, and the meanings behind specific colors, audiences can gain a deeper appreciation for the cultural heritage being represented. Incorporating personal anecdotes or legends related to the Jisum robes can humanize the cultural experience (Li, Zeng, & Tay, 2024). For instance, stories about individuals who wore these robes during significant events can create emotional connections, making the history more relatable and impactful (Yuxin et al., 2024).

The colours of the Jisum robes are each imbued with specific meanings, which can be explored through storytelling. For example, by narrating the significance of red as a symbol of celebration and power, audiences can gain a deeper understanding of its importance in Mongolian culture. This exploration can be further enhanced through the use of visual aids, such as displays of the robes in various colours, which allow attendees to observe the symbolism in action. Festivals can organise storytelling sessions that focus on themes associated with the colours of the Jisum robes. For instance, a day dedicated to the colour blue could feature stories about the sky, freedom, and nature, engaging the audience's imagination and encouraging them to reflect on their own connections to these themes. Engaging the audience in storytelling can create

a more dynamic experience (Yuxin et al., 2024). This could involve inviting attendees to share their interpretations of the colours or their own cultural stories related to clothing and identity. Such participation fosters a sense of community and shared experience (Ashraf et al., 2024).

Other opportunities may take the form of role-playing and reenactments, with festivals often incorporating role-playing activities where participants don Jisum robes and act out historical or mythical narratives. This immersive approach enables audience members to experience the cultural significance of the attire firsthand, thereby deepening their engagement and understanding. Interactive experiences play a crucial role in engaging audiences during cultural festivals, particularly when showcasing traditional elements like Jisum robes. By actively engaging attendees in the cultural narrative, these experiences foster a deeper connection to the heritage being presented. Hands-on workshops, such as those focusing on costume making and dyeing techniques, enable participants to engage creatively with the culture, providing insight into the craftsmanship and materials used in creating the vibrant colors of Jisum robes. Furthermore, cultural performances and role-playing activities, including theatrical reenactments and fashion shows, have been found to captivate audiences by inviting them to become part of the storytelling process (Li et al., 2024). This, in turn, has been shown to enhance their understanding of the cultural significance of the attire. Interactive exhibits further enhance audience engagement through touch-and-feel stations that allow attendees to experience the fabrics and materials used in Jisum robes.

Cultural exchange programs, incorporating collaborative activities and story-sharing circles, have been shown to promote dialogue and connection among attendees, thereby fostering a sense of community and shared learning (Juliana, Sihombing, & Antonio, 2025). The incorporation of live polls, surveys and social media has been demonstrated to encourage participation and feedback, thereby making attendees feel involved in the festival's direction. The incorporation of these interactive elements into the festival's structure serves to create a dynamic and immersive environment, with the dual objectives of educating attendees about the cultural significance of Jisum robes and fostering a deeper emotional connection to the traditions and stories that shape Mongolian heritage. Through active participation, audiences become co-creators of the cultural narrative, thereby ensuring that the legacy of the Yuan Dynasty and its traditional attire continues to resonate with future generations.

Figure 6: Story-Based Tourism Frameworks.

Final Considerations

The study of Jisum robes from the Yuan Dynasty (1271-1368) reveals a profound cultural diversity, as evidenced by their colour system, which integrates traditional Mongolian, Han Chinese, and Central Asian influences. These robes symbolise a unique cultural fusion, with colours representing power, purity, and social hierarchy, thereby underscoring their ceremonial significance. The incorporation of Central Asian dyeing techniques through the Silk Road further enriched their aesthetic appeal. The potential of Jisum robes to serve as a medium for cultural tourism and education through storytelling based tourism such like Cultural heritage exhibition, Role-playing, Reenactments, and cultural exchange program offering insights into the historical and cultural narratives of the Yuan Dynasty while suggesting areas for future exploration in the dynamic use of colours and cultural transmission pathways. This study provides a foundational understanding of the Jisum robes' colour system, it also identifies gaps in the dynamic use of colours and the specific pathways of cultural transmission. Future research could explore these areas further, enhancing our comprehension of the cultural and historical significance of Yuan Dynasty attire.

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Ethical Considerations

Not applicable

Conflict of Interest

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